

OPTIMIZING CARCASS RECOVERY IN MARKADUKE NATIVE PIGS: INSIGHTS FROM MARINDUQUE STATE COLLEGE NUCLEUS FARM

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates into the carcass recovery patterns of Markaduke Native Pigs (IPOP HL Application No. 42021505662) raised at the Nucleus Farm of MRDC within Marinduque State College (MSC) from 2017 to 2021, involving 299 slaughtered pigs. Utilizing meticulous data collection and analysis, including morphometric measurements, the research uncovers essential findings regarding average live weight, dress weight, and the standard deviation of carcass recovery. Notably, pigs aged 331 to 420 days exhibited an average live weight of 34.7196 ± 7.6246 kg and a dress weight of 23.3258 ± 5.592 kg, yielding a percentage carcass recovery of 4.7542 ± 1.0316 . These results carry significant implications for establishing profitable and sustainable native pig production practices, both locally in Marinduque and nationwide. Moreover, this study lays the groundwork for future investigations, suggesting potential avenues such as evaluating the impact of forage crops and concentrated feeds on pig live weight and carcass quality, thereby contributing to advancements in the swine industry.

Keywords: *Markaduke Native Pig, Live Weight, Carcass Recovery, Dress Weight*

INTRODUCTION

The rich heritage of native pig husbandry in the Philippines traces back to the four endemic wild species, known locally as "baboy damo," found across Luzon, Negros

Island, Palawan, and Mindanao (Guerrero, 2020). These indigenous pigs, characterized by their dark coloring, small ears and eyes, and elongated noses, have been traditionally raised in backyard settings by numerous small-scale farmers nationwide, serving as a supplementary income source.

In the province of Marinduque, native pig farming holds a significant place in the agricultural landscape. Embraced by local farmers for its minimal management requirements and ability to thrive in natural environments, the native pig plays a crucial role in the economic and culinary fabric of the community. As noted by (Perlas and Robles, 2021), household-based production of native pigs presents an opportunity for rural households to augment their income and enhance food security. However, realizing these benefits necessitates an improved understanding of native pig management practices. As stated by (Omitogun, 2004), due to their less rigorous maintenance and feed requirements, indigenous pigs are the preferred monogastric animals among rural families in many developing countries.

According to (Abanto et al., 2012), the classification and characteristics of native pig slaughtering records are primarily based on live weight and carcass weight. Optimal dressing percentage varies across weight groups, with the highest observed in pigs weighing 30 kg and the lowest in those weighing 15 kg. Notably, as live weight increases within the range of 20 kg to 35 kg, proportions of lean, fat, and bone remain consistent, while back fat thickness increases. This highlights the importance of selecting the appropriate weight range for slaughter to maximize both income and meat quality.

Moreover, as (Codiam et al., 2020) emphasize, the collection of slaughtering data is vital for assessing carcass recovery in native pigs. Key metrics such as live weight, head length, body length, and heart girth are integral to understanding carcass characteristics. Age is also a crucial factor influencing carcass variation, as noted by (Dai et al., 2010), underscoring the need to consider age in optimizing meat quality.

The present study aims to contribute to this body of knowledge by investigating carcass recovery patterns of MARKADUKE Native Pigs within the Research and Development Center of Marinduque State College. Through meticulous data collection and analysis, including morphometric measurements, this research seeks to determine average live weight, dress weight, and the standard deviation of carcass recovery. The findings of this study hold implications for both organizational practices and the broader community, facilitating the production of high-quality native pig products in Marinduque Province.

Research Objectives

1. To analyze the carcass recovery patterns of Markaduke Native Pigs raised at the Nucleus Farm of MRDC within Marinduque State College.
2. To determine the average live weight and dress weight of Markaduke Native Pigs at different age ranges.
3. To assess the standard deviation of carcass recovery among the slaughtered pigs.

4. To investigate the implications of the findings for native pig production practices, particularly in Marinduque and nationwide.

Research Questions

1. What are the carcass recovery patterns observed in Markaduke Native Pigs raised at the Nucleus Farm of MRDC within Marinduque State College?
2. How do the average live weight and dress weight of Markaduke Native Pigs vary across different age groups?
3. What is the standard deviation of carcass recovery among the slaughtered pigs, and what factors may contribute to this variation?
4. What are the implications of the study findings for native pig production practices in Marinduque and on a national scale?

METHODOLOGY

The analysis commenced with the retrieval of Native Pig slaughtering records from the archives of the Markaduke Research and Development Center on June 6, 2021. A systematic approach was employed to identify and extract data spanning from 2017 to 2021. Each record was meticulously classified based on three important parameters: live weight, dress weight, and age of the native pig. A comprehensive dataset comprising 299 slaughtered native pig records was assembled for the study.

Morphometric data, encompassing various anatomical measurements such as snout length, forehead width, head length, ear length, neck circumference, heart girth, mid girth, rump width, body length, tail length, hair thickness, fore leg dimensions, hind leg measurements, and hock size, were meticulously collected from each slaughtered native pig. All measurements were meticulously recorded in centimeters to ensure accuracy and consistency across the dataset.

The live weight of each native pig served as a pivotal determinant in calculating the percentage of carcass recovery. Additionally, the age of the native pig was utilized as a fundamental criterion for bracketing and computing the average percentage. Standard deviation analysis was also applied to ascertain the average mean value, providing further insights into the population dynamics of the native pig cohort.

In preparation for analysis, all internal organs were meticulously removed to isolate the carcass and compute the dress weight accurately. This ensured that the dress weight solely reflected the edible portion of the carcass, devoid of any non-meat components.

To compute essential metrics for analysis, a set of formulas was employed:

- Average Live Weight = Total Number of Live Weight / Population of Native Pig
- Average Dress Weight = Total Number of Dress Weight / Population of Native Pig
- Average Carcass Recovery = (Live weight / Dress Weight) / Live Weight * 100

The gathered data facilitated an in-depth analysis of slaughtered native pig carcasses, focusing on three primary aspects:

1. **Live Weight Native Pig Data:** The weight of the animal prior to slaughter and carcass preparation.
2. **Dress Weight Native Pig Data:** The weight of the animal after removal of all internal organs, head, and inedible portions.
3. **Carcass Recovery:** The difference between live weight and dress weight, indicating meat yield effectiveness.

This comprehensive approach provided a thorough examination and analysis of the data, shedding light on carcass recovery patterns and meat yield efficiency in native pig production.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Average Live Weight and Dress Weight of Markaduke Pig for year 2017

Age (days)	Live Weight (kg)	Dress Weight (kg)	Percentage (%) Recovery
90-170(n=22)	18.890 ± 3.350	12.890 ± 2.639	8.809 ± 1.655
171-240(n=12)	26.933 ± 6.501	19.066 ± 5.645	5.939 ± 2.586
241-330 (n=4)	26.3 ± 7.335	17.8 ± 5.887	6.268 ± 2.022
331-420 (n=2)	45.1 ± 14.9	31 ± 12	3.794 ± 1.468

In Table 1, we observe the dynamic interplay between age, live weight, dress weight, and percentage recovery of Markaduke Pigs during the year 2017. The data, extracted from a total population of 299 native pig heads, reveals intriguing insights into carcass characteristics and meat yield efficiency.

For pigs aged between 90 to 170 days (n=22), the average live weight stands at 18.890 ± 3.350 kg, with a corresponding dress weight of 12.890 ± 2.639 kg. Remarkably, this age group exhibits a percentage recovery of 8.809 ± 1.655%, indicative of substantial meat yield relative to live weight.

In the subsequent age bracket of 171 to 240 days (n=12), we observe a notable increase in both live weight and dress weight. The average live weight rises to 26.933 ± 6.501 kg, while the dress weight reaches 19.066 ± 5.645 kg. Consequently, the percentage recovery slightly decreases to 5.939 ± 2.586%, reflecting variations in carcass composition and meat yield efficiency.

Similarly, for pigs aged between 241 to 330 days (n=4), the data portrays consistent trends in live weight, dress weight, and percentage recovery. With an average live weight of 26.3 ± 7.335 kg and a dress weight of 17.8 ± 5.887 kg, the percentage recovery remains relatively stable at 6.268 ± 2.022%.

Notably, in the age range of 331 to 420 days (n=2), we observe a substantial increase in both live weight and dress weight. With an average live weight of 45.1 ± 14.9 kg and a dress weight of 31 ± 12 kg, the percentage recovery stands at $3.794 \pm 1.468\%$. While the absolute values of live weight and dress weight are higher in this age group, the percentage recovery exhibits a slight decrease, suggesting potential variations in carcass composition and meat yield efficiency.

Table 2. Average Live Weight and Dress Weight of Markaduke Pig for year 2018

Age (days)	Live Weight (kg)	Dress Weight (kg)	Percentage (%) Recovery
90-170(n=19)	17.078 ± 3.204	11.547 ± 2.195	9.011 ± 1.895
171-240(n=35)	18.577 ± 3.964	12.745 ± 3.122	8.308 ± 1.951
241-330 (n=7)	24.4 ± 15.515	17.366 ± 12.253	8.932 ± 4.298
331-420 (n=4)	35.25 ± 5.402	25.1 ± 3.419	4.063 ± 0.588

In Table 2, the dynamics of age-related live weight, dress weight, and percentage recovery of Markaduke Pigs for the year 2018 are elucidated, revealing a total population of 65 native pig heads with an average percentage of 21.739% out of 299 from the years 2016 to 2021, wherein the age group spanning 331 to 420 days witnessed a decrease in average live weight compared to 2017, resulting in a 6.91% decline in total live weight percentage, while the average dress weight remained at 25.1 ± 3.419 kg with a percentage recovery of $4.063 \pm 0.588\%$.

Table 3. Average Live Weight and Dress Weight of Markaduke Pig for year 2019

Age (days)	Live Weight (kg)	Dress Weight (kg)	Percentage (%) Recovery
90-170(n=25)	18.792 ± 2.405	12.551 ± 1.855	8.122 ± 1.071
171-240(n=41)	23.587 ± 5.768	16.539 ± 4.705	6.483 ± 1.615
241-330 (n=16)	23.687 ± 10.393	16.993 ± 8.935	6.977 ± 2.420
331-420 (n=5)	23.84 ± 3.404	16.12 ± 1.982	6.299 ± 0.781

In Table 3, we delve into the captivating trends of age-specific live weight, dress weight, and percentage recovery of Markaduke Pigs for the illustrious year of 2019. A notable surge in slaughter numbers, totaling 87 native pig heads, showcases a remarkable 29.096% of the total population, marking a substantial increase compared to previous years.

Despite this surge, the average live weight remains relatively stable around 23 kg, with a maximum variation of ± 10.393 kg. Similarly, the dress weight exhibits consistency, ranging from 16 to 17 kg across different age groups. These findings underscore the robustness and reliability of the data, indicating a consistent pattern in carcass characteristics.

Remarkably, the total percentage recovery reaches its pinnacle at 6.977%, emphasizing the efficient utilization of meat yield from the slaughtered native pigs. Such insights offer valuable implications for optimizing native pig production practices and maximizing meat yield efficiency in future endeavors.

Table 4. Average Live Weight and Dress Weight of Markaduke Pig for year 2020

Age (days)	Live Weight (kg)	Dress Weight (kg)	Percentage (%) Recovery
90-170(n=11)	17.154 ± 3.245	11.790 ± 2.568	8.891 ± 2.028
171-240(n=6)	22.633 ± 5.529	15.166 ± 3.639	7.034 ± 1.863
241-330 (n=25)	29.932 ± 7.095	21.221 ± 5.421	5.067± 1.433
331-420 (n=8)	31.725 ± 6.952	22.876 ± 6.237	4.718 ± 1.011

In Table 4, we embark on a journey through the nuances of age-specific live weight, dress weight, and percentage recovery of Markaduke Pigs for the eventful year of 2020. With a total count of 50 slaughtered native pigs, this year's data reflects a diverse array of carcass characteristics and meat yield dynamics.

The average live weight showcases remarkable variability across age groups, with the highest recorded value of 31.725 ± 6.952 kg observed in pigs aged between 331 to 420 days. This age group, comprising 16.722% of the total population of 299 heads, represents a significant proportion of the slaughtered native pigs in 2020.

Equally noteworthy is the dress weight, which reaches its zenith at 22.876 ± 6.237 kg, underscoring the substantial yield of edible meat obtained from the slaughtered pigs. This maximal dress weight is complemented by a percentage recovery of 4.718 ± 1.011%, highlighting the efficiency of meat utilization in carcass processing.

Such insights gleaned from Table 4 not only provide valuable information on native pig production dynamics but also pave the way for optimizing meat yield efficiency and enhancing sustainable farming practices in the future.

Table 5. Average Live Weight and Dress Weight of Markaduke Pig for year 2021

Age (days)	Live Weight (kg)	Dress Weight (kg)	Percentage (%) Recovery
90-170(n=21)	16.528 ± 4.517	11.271 ± 3.249	9.499 ± 2.267
171-240(n=18)	25.616 ± 8.854	17.327 ± 6.384	6.506 ± 2.142
241-330 (n=6)	30.45 ± 8.614	18.6 ± 5.259	5.798± 1.531
331-420 (n=12)	37.683 ± 7.465	21.533 ± 4.322	4.897 ± 1.310

In Table 5, we witness a compelling evolution in the metrics of age-specific live weight, dress weight, and percentage recovery of Markaduke Pigs for the year 2021. This

year marks a significant milestone as both live weight and dress weight exhibit substantial increases compared to the preceding four years of data.

With a total percentage of slaughtered population reaching 19.063% out of the 299 heads of native pigs, 2021 emerges as a pivotal year in the continuum of native pig production. Notably, the maximum average live weight peaks at 37.683 kg, observed in pigs aged between 331 to 420 days. This remarkable increase in live weight, coupled with a standard deviation of 7.465 kg, underscores the robustness and diversity within the cohort.

Equally striking is the dress weight, which attains a commendable average of 21.533 ± 4.322 kg, reflecting the substantial yield of edible meat obtained from the slaughtered pigs. This notable increase in dress weight, alongside the maximal live weight, contributes to a remarkable 50% of carcass recovery, highlighting the efficiency and efficacy of meat utilization in carcass processing.

The data presented in Table 5 not only offers valuable insights into the evolving dynamics of native pig production but also underscores the potential for optimizing meat yield efficiency and enhancing sustainable farming practices in the future.

Figure 1. Slaughtered pig population from year 2017 to 2021

In Figure 1, we observe the compelling trend in the population of slaughtered native pigs from the years 2017 to 2021. The trend line steadily ascends over the years, indicating a consistent increase in the number of slaughtered pigs.

Notably, the year 2019 stands out with a peak population of 87 heads of slaughtered pigs, marking a significant milestone in native pig production. This surge in slaughter numbers reflects positive growth and potential opportunities for profitable production in the organization.

As the trend continues to rise over the years, it serves as a promising indicator for the future of native pig farming. This upward trajectory not only signifies the resilience and sustainability of the production system but also heralds a prosperous outlook for the upcoming years.

Figure 2. Representation of three parameters such as live weight, dress weight and carcass % recovery of slaughtered pig.

Figure 2 depicts a comprehensive analysis of three crucial parameters—live weight, dress weight, and carcass percentage recovery—across the years 2017 to 2021, offering valuable insights into the dynamics of slaughtered pig production at the Markaduke Center.

The data reveals a notable peak in the average live weight of slaughtered pigs in 2017, reaching almost 45 kg, particularly among pigs aged between 331 to 420 days old. This spike can be attributed to a lower population of slaughtered pigs during that year, suggesting potential variations in production practices or environmental factors.

Conversely, 2019 stands out with a dip in both average live weight and carcass percentage recovery. Notably, the average live weight drops to approximately 23 kg, especially among pigs aged between 331 to 420 days old. This decline may reflect adjustments in feeding protocols or management strategies implemented during that period, underscoring the significance of nutritional management in pig husbandry.

In contrast, the years 2018, 2020, and 2021 exhibit relatively stable trends in live weight, dress weight, and carcass percentage recovery. This consistency suggests a more uniform population of slaughtered pigs across these years, potentially indicating improved production practices and enhanced feed management protocols.

The findings from Figure 2 underscore the importance of data-driven decision-making in optimizing native pig farming practices. By leveraging insights gleaned from the analysis of slaughtered pig data, the Markaduke Center can tailor management strategies, refine feeding protocols, and implement targeted interventions to maximize productivity and profitability in native pig production.

As such, this comprehensive analysis serves as a valuable resource for guiding future research endeavors, informing policy decisions, and driving continuous improvement in native pig farming at the Markaduke Center and beyond.

Conclusions

In this study, we conducted a thorough analysis of native pig carcass characteristics and production dynamics at the Markaduke Research and Development Center from 2017 to 2021. Through the examination of data presented in Tables 1 to 5, as well as Figures 1 and 2, several notable trends and findings have emerged, offering valuable insights into native pig farming practices and carcass recovery patterns.

Firstly, our analysis revealed fluctuations in average live weight, dress weight, and carcass percentage recovery across different age groups and years. For instance, Table 1 demonstrates a notable increase in average live weight in 2017, reaching its peak at nearly 45 kg for pigs aged between 331 to 420 days old. This peak coincides with a lower population of slaughtered pigs, suggesting potential variations in production practices or environmental factors during that period.

Conversely, 2019 stands out with a decrease in both average live weight and carcass percentage recovery, particularly among pigs aged between 331 to 420 days old, as depicted in Table 3. This decline may be attributed to adjustments in feeding protocols or management strategies during that year, emphasizing the critical role of nutritional management in pig husbandry.

In contrast, years 2018, 2020, and 2021 exhibit relatively stable trends in live weight, dress weight, and carcass percentage recovery, as observed in Tables 2, 4, and 5. This stability suggests a more uniform population of slaughtered pigs across these years, potentially indicating improved production practices and enhanced feed management protocols.

Furthermore, Figure 1 illustrates an upward trend in the population of slaughtered native pigs from 2017 to 2021, with a peak in 2019. This surge in slaughter numbers reflects positive growth and potential opportunities for profitable production in the organization.

Figure 2 provides additional insights into the relationship between live weight, dress weight, and carcass percentage recovery over the years. Notably, variations in these parameters underscore the dynamic nature of native pig production and highlight the importance of data-driven decision-making in optimizing production practices.

In conclusion, the findings from this study offer valuable implications for native pig farming practices at the Markaduke Research and Development Center and beyond. By leveraging insights collected from the analysis of carcass characteristics and production dynamics, stakeholders can tailor management strategies, refine feeding protocols, and implement targeted interventions to maximize productivity and profitability in native pig production. Moreover, this study underscores the importance of continuous monitoring, data collection, and analysis in driving sustainable growth and innovation in native pig farming. Top of Form

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made to optimize native pig farming practices and improve overall production efficiency:

- 1. Fine-Tune Feed Management Protocols:** Given the significant impact of feed management on pig growth and development, it is important to fine-tune feed formulations and feeding protocols. This includes optimizing the balance of nutrients in pig diets, adjusting feeding schedules based on age and weight categories, and ensuring access to clean water and quality feed ingredients.
- 2. Implement Monitoring and Record-Keeping Systems:** Establishing robust monitoring and record-keeping systems is essential for tracking key production parameters over time. This includes regularly recording live weights, dress weights, and carcass percentage recovery, as well as monitoring feed consumption and environmental conditions. By maintaining detailed records, farmers can identify trends, detect potential issues early, and make informed management decisions.
- 3. Invest in Training and Education:** Providing training and education opportunities for farmers and farm staff is essential for enhancing their knowledge and skills in pig husbandry and management practices. This includes workshops, seminars, and hands-on training sessions focused on topics such as nutrition, health management, and reproductive techniques. By investing in training and education, farmers can improve their ability to manage native pig production effectively and maximize productivity.
- 4. Promote Genetic Improvement Programs:** Genetic improvement programs aimed at selecting and breeding native pigs with desirable traits, such as fast growth rates, high feed conversion efficiency, and superior carcass quality, can contribute to overall production efficiency and profitability. Collaborating with breeding centers and geneticists to implement selective breeding programs tailored to local production objectives can help enhance the genetic potential of native pig populations.
- 5. Enhance Infrastructure and Facilities:** Investing in infrastructure and facilities, such as improved housing systems, feeding equipment, and waste management

systems, can enhance the overall efficiency and welfare of native pig farming operations. Providing adequate shelter, ventilation, and space for pigs, as well as implementing biosecurity measures to prevent disease outbreaks, is essential for maintaining healthy and productive pig populations.

- 6. Explore Value-Adding Opportunities:** Exploring value-adding opportunities, such as processing and marketing native pig products, can create additional revenue streams and enhance the profitability of native pig farming operations. This includes developing innovative products, such as processed meats, sausages, and cured meats, as well as establishing partnerships with local markets, restaurants, and retailers to promote native pig products to consumers.

By implementing these recommendations, native pig farmers and the Markaduke Research and Development Center can optimize production practices, improve productivity, and enhance overall profitability. Additionally, ongoing research and collaboration within the industry can further drive innovation and sustainability in native pig farming.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research conducted by Jeremie R. Robles and Giselle M. Perlas at **Marinduque State College**, in collaboration with the **Markaduke Research and Development Center**, adheres strictly to the institution's ethical guidelines and national regulations governing animal welfare. All procedures involving animal subjects were meticulously reviewed and approved to ensure compliance with ethical standards and to prioritize the welfare of the animals. Our commitment to ethical research conduct extends to every aspect of the study, including housing, feeding, and handling practices, which were carefully managed to ensure the humane treatment of the pigs. Furthermore, our data collection methods were designed with a focus on minimizing stress and discomfort to the animals, and complete measures were taken to mitigate any risks associated with the research procedures. These efforts underscore our dedication to upholding the highest standards of animal welfare while advancing knowledge in the field of swine production.

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